

Farm profile

Farm's name: _____

Date of visit: ____/____/____

City/State: _____

Owner name/manager: _____

Contact phone: _____

E-mail: _____

1. Herd (technician)

- a) N° of lactating cows: _____ b) N° of suckling calves: _____ c) N° employees per calves: _____
- d) Average milk production/day: _____
- e) Collaborators system: () Employer () Familiar
- f) Predominant breed: () Holstein () Holstein x Gir () Jersey () Jersey x Gir () Gir
- g) Veterinary assistance: () Yes () No
- h) If yes, what frequency: () Bimonthly () Monthly () Biweekly () Weekly () Sporadically

2. Installations (technician)

- a) Suckling calves () Cages () Collective stalls () Individual stalls () Tropical () Mixed (according to age)
- b) Lactating cows () Pasture () Compost barn () Free stall () Trough () Mixed (according to age)
- c) Dry cows () Pasture () Compost barn () Free stall () Trough () Mixed (according to age)
- d) Parturition () Pasture () Compost barn () Free stall () Trough () Mixed (according to age)

3. Calf handling (technician + stockperson / manager)

- a) Colostrum - type of supply: () Sucks on mother () Bottle () Esophageal probe
- b) Colostrum - supply quantity : () Do not know, suck on mother () ≤ 2 liters () ≥ 3 liters () 10% of live weight
- c) Colostrum - type: () Fresh () Frozen () Dried () Enriched
- d) Colostrum - time until supply: () ≤ 2 hours () ≤ 6 hours () ≤ 12 hours () > 12 hours
- e) O colostro fornecido é: () Always from mother () Always from several mothers () Depends on the quality () Always stock colostrum
- f) Have colostrum stock: () Yes () No
- g) Analyzes the supplied colostrum: () Yes () No
- h) Analyzes stored colostrum: () Yes () No
- i) What is the method of evaluating colostrum: () Brix refractometer () Protein refractometer () Colostrobball () Colostrometer
- j) Calf suckling - method: () Milkbar () Bucket () Feeding bottle () Mixed (varies with age)
- k) Calf suckling - amount of milk: () Minimum 4 liters/day () Minimum 6 liters/day () Minimum 8 liters/day () Mixed (varies with age)
- l) Calf suckling - type of milk: () Fresh milk () Milk replacer () Waste milk () Acidified milk
- m) Calf suckling - use of waste milk: () Always use () Use only when milk price is high () Use only when milk replacer price is high
- n) Calf suckling - use of esophageal tube: () Always use () Only when the calf has difficulty suckling
- o) Calf suckling - weaning: () Age ≤ 60 days () Age 60 to 90 days () Weight ≥ 90 kg () Weight ≥ 120 kg
- p) Navel cure: () Yes, for 3 days () Yes, for 2 days () Yes, for 1 day () Does not cure navel

4. Sanity (technician + manager)

- a) SCC milk tank (last month): _____ b) UFC milk tank (last month): _____
- c) Weight of up to 3 calves in the week of birth: _____ d) Weight of up to 3 calves at weaning week: _____
- e) IPT evaluation (brix or protein refractometer) of up to 3 calves with a maximum age of 7 days: _____
- Obs.:** if it is not possible to measure with any of the refractometers, please collect the blood, freeze the serum in eppendorf, label and send to the laboratory.
- f) How many calves were observed during lactation: _____ g) How many calves showed clinical signs of respiratory disease (cough, nasal discharge or abnormal breathing) during lactation: _____
- h) How many calves showed clinical signs of diarrhea (dirty tail or liquid feces) during lactation: _____

- i) How many calves did not suckle during lactation: _____
- j) How many calves have omphalopathies: _____
- k) What is the annual mortality of suckling calves:
- () ≤ 5% () Between 5 and 10% () Between 10 and 15% () ≥ 15%
- l) What is the annual rate of dystocia (human assistance was needed):
- () ≤ 5% () Between 5 and 10% () Between 10 and 15% () ≥ 15%

5. Calf herd employees (individual for each of the employees - apply to all)

- a) Already trained the employees responsible for the calf: () Yes () No
- b) If yes, what is the frequency of training:
- () Once () Yearly () Semester () Quarterly
- c) Há quanto tempo o funcionário do bezerreiro está nessa função:
- () ≤ 1 year () 1 to 2 years () 2 to 5 years () ≥ 5 years
- d) What is the employee's gender?: () Man () Woman
- e) How old is the employee?:
- () From 18 to 25 years old () 26 and 35 years old () From 36 to 50 years old () > 50 years
- f) What is the employee's marital status?: () Married () Single
- g) The employee has children: () Yes () No
- h) Employee's education level:
- () Did not study () Elementary School () High school () University education
- i) Have you ever taken a technical course (agricultural school, SENAR, external training):
- () Yes () No
- j) Employee experience time with calf:
- () ≤ 1 year () 1 to 2 years () 2 to 5 years () ≥ 5 years
- k) Employee works exclusively in the calf:
- () 100% () 75% () 50% () 25%
- l) An employee takes notes on health occurrences: () Yes () No
- m) Employee participates in all management (breastfeeding, treatments, weaning):
- () Yes () No
- n) Interviewer, rate the employee's degree of satisfaction in working at the calf:
- () Very satisfied () Satisfied () Indifferent () Dissatisfied

Observations:
